

Thermodynamics of Ionic Association in Aqueous Copper Acetate Solutions using Spectrophotometric Method

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The stoichiometric, K , the thermodynamic, K_A , association constants, enthalpy change, ΔH° , entropy ΔS° , and free energy change, ΔG° for the association between Cu^{2+} and acetate ions are determined spectrophotometrically. The experimental conditions are arranged in such a way to obtain only 1:1 ion pair. Measurements are carried out at two ionic strengths ($I=0.06$ and $0.10 M$) at each of the three studied temperatures, 25° , 40° and 55° .

IN recent years great interest has been shown by the solution chemists to study the ionic association for some of the very common and classic systems by as many techniques as possible. One of the present authors has a series of publications¹⁻⁷ in which he and others have calculated the thermodynamic association constants of many 2-2, 2-1 and 1-2 salts in aqueous solutions in a very wide experimental conditions using ion-selective electrode technique and spectrophotometric one.

The work on copper acetate attracted us from several points of view. The available data on this system is not a systematic one, it is rather scattered and in many ways not very well planned. Parameters using different techniques are practically impossible. Even in the few cases in which the authors thought that there was a reasonable information they were shocked by some trivial points in the experimental part, which caused almost fatal mistakes.

It was thought, therefore, to study this system under the proper experimental conditions using spectrophotometric techniques at various temperatures and ionic strengths.

Experimental

A. *Material*: Copper nitrate was analytical reagent and was recrystallized twice from deionized water. Sodium acetate, KNO_3 and HNO_3 were analytical reagents. Preparation and standardization of the solutions of Cu(II) nitrate, Na acetate, KNO_3 were made in principle by the same procedure as described in a previous paper⁸.

B. *Apparatus*: Measurements were made using a Zeiss QM3 Spectrophotometer equipped with 1 cm cell. The temperature of the solution was maintained constant. The temperature was controlled to $\pm 0.2^\circ$.

The experiments were carried out by mixing $\text{Cu(NO}_3)_2$ and sodium acetate in presence of KNO_3 and HNO_3 .

The HNO_3 was added to adjust the pH to 4.9 to prevent the hydrolysis of Cu^{2+} .

The concentrations of sodium acetate were always kept less than those of $\text{Cu(NO}_3)_2$ to keep the ratio of acetate to copper less than unity.

This should assure the formation of 1:1 ion pair, (CuAc^+) , mainly rather than 1:2 ion pairs (CuAc_2) .

Measurements and collecting data: Optical density (D) was determined at each temperature using 1 cm cell for the solution (D') and the reference (D). Copper nitrate was used as the reference and the sample contained sodium acetate and KNO_3 . ($D-D'$) was read directly and the measurements were repeated several times.

Representative data are shown in Tables 2-3.

TABLE 1—SUMMARY OF THE ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTH AND TEMP.

Temp $^\circ\text{C}$	I	K	K_A	K_A^{corr}	$\Delta\epsilon$	$f \pm$
25	0.06	39.70	91.2644	156.76	12.0	0.435
	0.1	34.50	91.03	156.36	19.34	0.379
40	0.06	53.75	123.197	214.264	9.3	0.436
	0.1	48.075	126.847	220.613	17.33	0.379
55	0.06	81.699	187.814	335.325	12.0	0.435
	0.1	69.119	182.374	325.611	10.33	0.379

Results and Discussion

A. *Mathematical model*:

We assume that there is an association between the copper cation (Cu^{2+}) and the acetate ion (Ac^-) to form the ion-pair (CuAc^+) in this aqueous media as 1:1 complex, as arranged experimentally. We can then represent this association by the following equation:

at equilibrium $a - x$ $b - x$ x

It is known that both free Cu^{2+} and CuAc^+ ion-pair absorb in the visible range. The measurements were carried out at a wavelength 780 nm. If Cu^{2+}

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and CuAc⁺ are the only two species absorbing at 780 nm, then using Beer's law we have ;

$$D = \epsilon l a \quad \text{but } l = 1$$

then $D = \epsilon a$

where D is the optical density of Cu²⁺, ϵ is the molar extinction coefficient of Cu²⁺(aq.), a is the concentration of Cu²⁺(aq.) and

$$D' = \epsilon' x + \epsilon(a - x)$$

where D' = optical density of CuAc⁺ and Cu²⁺(aq.) ions,

ϵ' = extinction coefficient of CuAc⁺, $(a - x) = \text{Cu}^{2+}$ in the sample solution.

$$\therefore D' - D = \Delta\epsilon \cdot x$$

but the stoichiometric association constant of CuAc⁺ is given by

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-x)}$$

Combining the above equations, we obtain

$$\frac{ab}{D' - D} = \frac{a + b - x}{\Delta\epsilon} + \frac{1}{\Delta\epsilon \cdot K}$$

where $\Delta\epsilon = \epsilon' - \epsilon$.

Our task now is to calculate both K and $\Delta\epsilon$, since the other parameters in the last equation are known

(except x). We used a graphical method, in which x is neglected first and $\frac{ab}{D' - D}$ is plotted against (a + b). From the slope and intercept both $\Delta\epsilon$ and K are obtained. A value of x is then obtained by

$$x = (a + b) + \frac{1}{K} - \frac{ab}{D' - D} \Delta\epsilon$$

then a new graph is plotted, between $\frac{ab}{D' - D}$ against (a + b - x). New values of K and $\Delta\epsilon$ are obtained. This process is repeated several times until constant values of x, K and $\Delta\epsilon$ are obtained. Two iterations were necessary to obtain such constant values.

Table 1 shows these results at 25, 40 and 55°.

B. Calculation of stoichiometric association constant K :

From the above derived relation we can then use an iterative procedure to obtain both K, x and $\Delta\epsilon$, the stoichiometric association constant, the concentration of the ion pair and the difference of extinction coefficient between the two species (Cu²⁺ and CuAc⁺) respectively.

Two or three iterations were enough to produce a constant value for x and consequently a constant value for K. We used the graphical method for

TABLE 2—STOICHIOMETRIC ASSOCIATION CONSTANT AND SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DATA OF COPPER ACETATE AT 25°

[CuNO ₃] a	[Ac ⁻] b	I	[KNO ₃] in CuNO ₃	[CuNO ₃] K ⁺ NO ₃ (D)	CuNO ₃ NaAc ⁺ K ⁺ NO ₃ D'	[KNO ₃] to fix I	a + b	D' - D	ab	$\frac{ab}{D' - D}$	$x = a + b + \frac{1}{K} - \frac{ab}{D' - D} \Delta\epsilon$	a + b - x
0.02	0.002	0.041	0.02	0.169	0.180	0.019	0.022	0.011	4 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.636 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.002875	0.01913
0.02	0.004	0.042	0.02	0.165	0.168	0.018	0.024	0.003	8 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.0267	0.02835	0.02595
0.02	0.006	0.043	0.02	0.181	0.181	0.017	0.026	0.0	1.2 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.0	0.05225	0.07825
0.02	0.008	0.044	0.02	0.153	0.189	0.016	0.028	0.036	1.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.4 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.00075	0.02725
0.02	0.01	0.045	0.02	0.154	0.230	0.015	0.03	0.076	2 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.36 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.02938	0.0066
0.02	0.012	0.046	0.02	0.171	0.217	0.014	0.032	0.046	2.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.2 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.00675	0.0388
0.02	0.014	0.048	0.02	0.157	0.216	0.012	0.034	0.059	2.2 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.7 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.00150	0.0325
0.02	0.016	0.050	0.02	0.178	0.255	0.01	0.036	0.077	3.2 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.16 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.01025	0.02575
0.02	0.018	0.052	0.02	0.157	0.217	0.008	0.038	0.06	3.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.01075	0.0488
0.02	0.02	0.054	0.02	0.171	0.216	0.006	0.04	0.045	4 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.9 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.04500	0.085

f ± = 0.435, $\Delta\epsilon = 12.0$, K = 39.70, I = 0.07895.

TABLE 3—STOICHIOMETRIC ASSOCIATION CONSTANT AND SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DATA OF COPPER ACETATE AT 25° AT I = 0.1112

[Cu ²⁺] a	[Ac ⁻] b	I	KNO ₃ in CuNO ₃	D	D'	a + b	ab	D' - D	$\frac{ab}{D' - D}$	$x = a + b + \frac{1}{K} - \frac{ab}{D' - D} \Delta\epsilon$	a + b - x
0.04	0.004	0.082	0.02	0.292	0.32	0.044	1.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.028	0.0067	0.0387	0.078
0.04	0.008	0.034	0.02	0.252	0.347	0.048	3.2 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.068	0.00470	0.01120	0.0592
0.04	0.012	0.036	0.02	0.262	0.363	0.052	4.8 × "	0.065	0.0048	0.0091	0.0611
0.04	0.016	0.038	0.02	0.297	0.425	0.056	6.4 × "	0.128	0.0050	0.0088	0.065
0.04	0.02	0.090	0.02	0.398	0.413	0.06	8.0 × "	0.016	0.00635	0.02973	0.0897
0.04	0.024	0.032	0.02	0.294	0.501	0.064	0.6 × "	0.120	0.0080	0.0562	0.1202
0.04	0.028	0.034	0.02	0.308	0.419	0.068	1.2 × 10 ⁻³	0.110	0.0109	0.10585	0.1739
0.04	0.032	0.036	0.02	0.268	0.475	0.072	1.2 × "	0.207	0.00618	0.01490	0.087
0.04	0.036	0.038	0.02	0.282	0.510	0.076	1.44 × "	0.228	0.0063	0.01275	0.089
0.04	0.040	0.10	0.02	0.298	0.536	0.08	1.6 × 10 ⁻³	0.238	0.0067	0.01620	0.096

f ± = 0.379, $\Delta\epsilon = 19.84$, K = 84.50, I = 0.112.

iteration instead of using computerized procedure. A sample of these data are shown in Tables 1-3.

C. Calculation of thermodynamic association constant (K_A):

Having obtained the stoichiometric association constants K at the various ionic strengths of the proper temperatures, we calculate the activity coefficient at these ionic strengths using Davies equation

$$\log f_{\pm} = -0.5 Z^2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{I}}{1 + \sqrt{I}} - 0.3 I \right)$$

To calculate the thermodynamic association constants (K_A) from the stoichiometric association constant, (K) we use the following equation:

$$K_A = K \frac{1}{f_{Cu}^{+2}}$$

The data are shown in Table 1.

D. Correction for cationic and anionic hydrolysis:

There was no correction for the cationic hydrolysis (Cu^{2+}), since at the measured pH (4.9) the hydrolysis of Cu^{2+} is almost negligible. Therefore no correction was necessary for Cu^{2+} hydrolysis. However, correction for the acetate ion at this pH is necessary. If one works out the equations we obtain the following equation:

$$K_A^{corr} = K_A \left(1 + \frac{[H^+]}{K_a} \right)$$

where K_A^{corr} is the corrected thermodynamic association constants for hydrolysis, $[H^+] =$ the concentration of the hydrogen ion and K_a is the dissociation constant of acetic acid.

E. Calculation of ΔS° , ΔH° and ΔG° parameters:

ΔH° was obtained from variation of K_A^{corr} with temperature and $\Delta G^\circ = RT \ln K_A^{corr}$.

Then using ΔH° and ΔG° , ΔS° is obtained at each studied temperatures from the following relationship:

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T \Delta S^\circ$$

$$\therefore \Delta S^\circ = \frac{\Delta G^\circ - \Delta H^\circ}{T}$$

Table 4 summarizes all the thermodynamic results obtained in this work and others.

It is seen that only scattered results are available from literature and far away from each other. For example, K_A obtained from spectra by Aditya⁸ is $83.3 M^{-1}$. K_A from glass electrode technique is $331 M^{-1}$.¹¹ This is really a vast difference and the authors could not explain their differences. We find however, that our results at 25° is very much comparable to those of Archer and Monk¹⁴ by

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF IONIC ASSOCIATION OF COPPER ACETATE, USING VARIOUS METHODS

Temp °C	Method	K_A^{corr}	ΔH° Kcal/mol	ΔG° Kcal/mol	ΔS° cal M^{-1} $^\circ K^{-1}$
25	Spectro	156.5 ¹⁰	3.0	-3.0119	20.162
40	"	217.4 ¹⁰	"	-3.3691	20.397
55	"	330.4 ¹⁰	"	-3.8051	20.737
25	Ion-selective	151.8 ⁸	—	—	—
35	Spectra	83.3 ⁸	—	—	—
25	glassselect.	331 ¹¹	—	—	—
25	quhyd	74.1 ⁹	—	—	—
20	glassselect.	77.7 ¹²	—	—	—
25	"	169.8 ¹⁴	—	—	—

glass electrode technique and those of Emara⁵ and Farid by ion selective electrode technique.

This is an encouraging sign that our results are in a reasonable accuracy, specially it has been reported for the data Ca and Mg acetate to that of Archer and Monk are among the very trustable results and comparable with those obtained by ultrasonic techniques⁹.

The fact that our spectrophotometric results at 25° ($156.5 M^{-1}$)¹⁰ is comparable to those obtained from glass electrode ($169.8 M^{-1}$) and ion-selective electrode ($151.8 M^{-1}$)⁸ indicates that the association of copper acetate takes place in a simple fashion and in one form either, outer-sphere or inner sphere only, and not both as shown in case of Cu sulphate.

The thermodynamic parameters such as ΔH° indicates that this association step is an endothermic one with about 3 K cal/mole. Which is a reasonable value.

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